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GRADUATE STUDENTS INNOVATE TEACHING DEVICES IN RESEARCH PROJECTS

ROMEL R. COSTALES, PH.D.

Associate Professor IV

*Isabela State University-City of Ilagan Campus
Isabela Province, Region 02, Philippines*

Five students enrolled in the Master of Arts in Industrial Education (MAIE) major in Technology and Home Economics program at Isabela State University-City of Ilagan Campus have developed groundbreaking teaching devices as part of their research projects during the Academic Year 2023-2024.

These teaching devices are the students' outputs in their developmental research or thesis. They primarily aim to improve instructional delivery and address the shortage of Instructional Materials (IMs) at both secondary and tertiary levels in various technical-vocational subjects, covering electronics and electricity education, agricultural technology education, and beauty care and wellness.

Mr. Joan Dioso, a graduating masteral student who currently teaches electronics education at a trade school, conducted a study titled "Development and Evaluation of Hybrid Photovoltaic Electrical System Modular Trainer". This trainer is a valuable resource for high school students, providing hands-on learning experiences in electrical and electronics education while aligning with industry standards.

An Electrical Installation, Fire Detection, Alarm System, and Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) System Trainer was developed by Emil Joey Turqueza. The integrated trainer seeks to enhance the technical skills of learners in electrical majors, preparing them to meet industry standards and certifications. Just like Dioso's trainer, Turqueza's teaching device prepares students to pass the National Certification (NC) II assessment by the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA).

Moreover, aiming to contribute to the improvement of agricultural education in the country, Leonardo Vea ventured into designing and creating a solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow as an instructional material in Agri-Crops Production. This trainer aims to enhance the student's practical learning experiences in agricultural and technical education.

Meanwhile, Gian Carlo Marcelo, another MAIE-THE graduating student made a remarkable contribution to the advancement of Electronics Education through his research "Development and Evaluation of a Modular Integrated Amplifier Simulator." This instructional tool provides high school students with hands-on training to develop and enhance their practical skills and comprehensive knowledge of electronics.

In the field of beauty care and wellness, Elizabeth Abrenilla built a "Multi-purpose Vanity Bed." This versatile piece of furniture, accented with rattan, serves as a laboratory material for teaching various shopwork activities, including facial treatments, shampooing, make-up application, body massage, manicures, and pedicures.

Experts have deemed all the research outputs by the MAIE students to be highly effective educational tools. These devices bridge the gap between pedagogical theory and practice in technical and vocational education.

Notably, the graduate students' research works have been published in reputable international peer-reviewed journals, thus advancing knowledge in their respective fields. These contributions not only add to the existing body of literature but also lay the groundwork for future research endeavors.

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